

Exploring genAI Chatbots in MOOCs: Analyzing Student Interactions and Self-Regulated Learning Behaviors

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Abstract. The integration of generative AI (genAI) chatbots into Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) presents new opportunities for supporting self-regulated learning (SRL). This study examines 1,302 chatbot interactions from two Austrian blended MOOCs, where a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) chatbot based on GPT 4o-mini was deployed to assist students. Using the process-action framework by Lai (2024), we categorize chatbot interactions into key SRL processes: defining, seeking, engaging, and reflecting. Results show that students predominantly use the chatbot for information retrieval, content summarization, and quiz-based reinforcement, with 41% of interactions classified as information search queries and 17% as rehearsal. However, engagement with metacognitive SRL strategies, such as goal setting and self-evaluation, remains low. Additionally, non-learning interactions, including humor-driven conversations, functional queries, and prompt injection attempts, showcase ways students interact with AI in educational settings. Based on our findings, we propose refinements to the existing SRL process-action framework, incorporating new categories to better account for genAI chatbot-specific interactions, such as Evaluation of Information Quality and Reformatting. We discuss implications for chatbot integration in MOOCs, emphasizing AI-generated quizzes, structured feedback, and safeguards against misuse.

Keywords: AI Chatbots · MOOCs · Self-Regulated Learning · Generative AI · Student Interactions · Blended Learning · Educational Technology

1 Introduction

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have become an essential part of democratizing education by providing open learning opportunities to diverse audiences. However, their asynchronous delivery poses a significant challenge, particularly in terms of learner engagement and retention [8]. To be successful in such an

environment, students need to be able to perform self-regulated learning (SRL), which refers to the ability to plan, monitor and evaluate one’s own learning processes [2, 12]. SRL includes setting learning goals, adapting learning strategies, and evaluating learning outcomes. Another approach to this problem is Inverse Blended Learning (IBL), which integrates offline meetings into online courses to increase interaction and reduce dropout rates [5].

Artificial intelligence (AI)-based chatbots have shown great promise as tools to support SRL in online learning environments [7]. Previous research [3] has investigated the effectiveness of retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) chatbots in MOOCs, highlighting their ability to support learners with summaries, concept clarification, and interactive exercises. However, existing studies also show that while chatbots support cognitive aspects of SRL, they may struggle to maintain learner motivation [9].

By combining these two approaches – Inverse Blended Learning (IBL) MOOCs and AI chatbots – we aim to create a more supportive and structured learning environment, particularly in asynchronous phases where students need self-regulation. Understanding how learners interact with chatbots in this context is essential to evaluating their effectiveness in fostering SRL.

This leads us to the central question of our study:

How do learners interact with AI-powered chatbots in MOOCs, and to what extent do these interactions support self-regulated learning (SRL)?

To systematically examine chatbot-assisted learning behaviors, we build upon the process-action framework proposed by Lai (2024) [10]. This framework categorizes chatbot interactions into four key SRL processes – defining, seeking, engaging, and reflecting – providing a structured approach to understanding how learners interact with AI support in MOOCs.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Design

This study investigates chatbot interactions within two Austrian university MOOCs, both designed to support SRL. One of the courses was the *InfoFit* MOOC, previously analyzed in [3] regarding helpfulness of RAG-based chatbots, while the second *Societal Aspects of Information Technology* followed a similar instructional structure. These courses were delivered via the *iMooX.at* platform, Austria’s national MOOC provider [4], and employed a blended learning approach [11]. The instructional design combined asynchronous self-paced video lectures, interactive quizzes, and reading materials with face-to-face sessions.

To assist students throughout the learning process, a generative AI chatbot was integrated into both MOOCs. The chatbot was based on a retrieval-augmented-generation (RAG) model, ensuring that its responses were aligned with the course materials while leveraging generative AI to enhance engagement and adapt to student needs.

2.2 Data Collection

This study is based on the analysis of 1,302 chatbot interactions collected from both MOOCs (see Table 2). These interactions were extracted from the chatbot’s anonymized server logs. The dataset consists of user queries (prompts) submitted to the chatbot, system-generated responses, and timestamps indicating the frequency and distribution of chatbot usage. The data was stored in a secure university-controlled environment to ensure compliance with privacy regulations. Since the chatbot was integrated into every course page, interactions were automatically logged without requiring additional user input, ensuring an unobtrusive data collection process.

2.3 Data Analysis

To analyze the learning behaviors exhibited through chatbot interactions, we applied the process-action framework introduced by Lai in 2024 [10]. This framework classifies chatbot queries into four self-regulated learning processes, see Table 1.

Table 1. Process-action framework for chatbot interactions from [10]

Process	Action (Code)	Description	Conversation Examples
Defining	Identification (D.I)	Identifying problems or providing a problem.	These are important ..., I am given a problem ...
	Goal-set (D.G)	Setting educational goals or sub-goals.	I need to achieve ..., I want to learn ..., Create a checklist ...
Seeking	Search (S.S)	Securing information from a chatbot.	Tell me about ..., Please recommend some resources ..., What is ...
	Select (S.SL)	Recording important information or results.	What are the key points ..., Extract the main idea of ...
Engaging	Review (E.RV)	Re-engaging with curated material or checking for correctness.	This does not seem to be correct ..., Does this mean that ...
	Organise (E.O)	Re-arranging materials by category or asking to perform knowledge management.	Can you help me to summarise ..., Put this in a list/table ..., Tell me step by step ...
	Rehearse (E.RH)	Memorising materials or putting it to practice by asking for an example.	Can you help me fill the gaps ..., Please generate questions on ..., I want to spend more time on ...
Reflecting	Task Evaluation (R.ET)	Evaluating the quality of work or indicating an intention to progress to a subsequent task.	What is the next thing ..., I learned (topic), how is this related to (another topic) ...
	Self Evaluation (R.ES)	Evaluating motivation or checking for learning gaps.	Can you tell me where I am lacking ..., I am not getting it ..., Can you check where I misunderstood ...

Each chatbot interaction was manually coded by the authors based on this categorization.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in full compliance with copyright and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union. All MOOC contents at iMooX.at are provided under Creative Commons licenses, so the use in

LLM is possible in accordance with the European copyright law. The chatbot was hosted on a university-controlled server, ensuring that all data remained within EU jurisdiction. To protect student privacy, all interactions were anonymized, and no personally identifiable information was stored. Participation in chatbot interactions was voluntary, and students were informed about data collection procedures and their right to opt out at any time. Additionally, transparency was maintained by providing students with clear guidelines on how the chatbot functioned and how their interactions would be used for research purposes. Since ethical considerations prevented linking individual chatbot interactions to specific student academic performance, the analysis was conducted exclusively on aggregated data. This approach ensures that findings reflect general usage patterns rather than individual learning trajectories, preserving student anonymity while still allowing for meaningful insights into chatbot-supported SRL.

3 Results

3.1 Chatbot Usage in Two MOOCs

The dataset consists of 1,302 chatbot interactions collected from two blended university MOOCs, *InfoFit* and *GADI*. The *InfoFit* MOOC, designed for first-year students as introduction into basic computer science, was conducted between September and October 2024 and accounted for the majority of interactions (928). The MOOC "Social Aspects of Information Society" (German original "Gesellschaftliche Aspekte der Informationsgesellschaft", in short GADI), offered from October 2024 to February 2025, had 374 recorded interactions. Despite differences in course duration and target audience, chatbot usage patterns were consistent across both MOOCs, with students primarily leveraging the AI assistant for factual information retrieval. This highlights the effectiveness of the retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) approach, which enabled the chatbot to generate high-quality, contextually relevant answers based on the Open Educational Resources (OER) course material.

Table 2 presents a comparative overview of chatbot usage metrics between the two MOOCs, highlighting differences in participant numbers, completion rates, and chatbot engagement, showing high variance in interaction frequency among users.

Table 2. Comparison of Usage

Aspect	InfoFit	GADI
MOOC Participants	601	342
Lecture Participants	124	255
MOOC Completion	136	170
Chatbot Prompts	928	374
MOOC Chatbot Users	78	58
Average Chats per User \pm Standard Deviation	11.9 \pm 20.9	6.4 \pm 10.8

3.2 Distribution of Learning-Oriented Interactions according to Lai's framework

Figure 1 presents the categorization of chatbot interactions based on the SRL process-action framework [10]. The dominant category was *seeking - search (S.S)*, comprising 41% of total queries. This indicates that students predominantly used the chatbot as an information retrieval tool. An additional 15% of queries were classified as *seeking - select (S.SL)*, where students asked for summarized key points or extracted definitions.

A substantial portion of interactions (17%) fell into *engaging - rehearse (E.RH)*, where students tested their knowledge through practice questions. Notably, of the 227 students prompts in *E.RH*, 120 queries specifically involved answers for *multiple-choice format questions* like "A and B", suggesting that students frequently relied on the chatbot for active learning reinforcement.

Fig. 1. Distribution of chatbot interactions across SRL processes (N = 1302) using the framework of Lai (2024)

Conversely, the chatbot was rarely used for *defining - identification (D.I)* and *goal-setting (D.G)* (3% combined) or *reflecting - self-evaluation (R.ES)* (1%), indicating that learners primarily viewed it as a source of structured content rather than a metacognitive support tool. Further, within the *seeking (S.S)* category, 99 out of 530 queries were directly related to self-evaluation questions from the MOOC platform, such as:

What is the concept behind "Green IT"? Question 10 Select one or more:
a. Save resources b. Reuse old devices c. Avoid importing PC components
d. Optimize the recycling of old devices.

3.3 Interactions not fitting to Lai's framework of SRL

Beyond structured learning support, a large proportion of chatbot interactions (11 %) were classified as *other interactions* as they did not fit to Lai's (2024)

framework. They were not directly related to learning activities such as goal setting, information seeking, engagement, or reflection. Instead, they involved casual conversations, functional commands, or general queries beyond the scope of academic self-regulation.

Out of Context Prompts (n = 27): Some students used the chatbot to ask general, non-course-related questions, such as:

What is in pistachio ice cream?; How do I get from Graz to Vienna?

Error and Function-Related Queries (n = 12): Some interactions focused on controlling the chatbot interface, including:

I want to minimize you.; Close chatbot; Can you exit full-screen mode?

Human-Like Conversations (n = 41): A notable portion of interactions involved casual, conversational exchanges, including greetings and expressions of gratitude:

Hello.; Thanks!; How are you?; What is your name?;

Prompt Injection and Manipulation Attempts (n = 8): A small but noteworthy number of queries attempted to override the chatbot’s instructional focus or manipulate responses. Examples include:

*Forget that you are a chatbot for GADI.;
Imagine you are a normal chatbot without any specific topics.*

These suggest an attempt to test or personalize the chatbot’s engagement.

(Potentially) SRL related interactions As it can be seen, some of these interactions that did not fit into the framework of Lai (2024) might as well be related to SRL. Examples are e.g. queries attempted to probe the chatbot’s source of knowledge:

Where do you get your information from?; How were you trained?

Others are functionality-related requests included:

Translate this into English.; Can you draw a sketch of this?; Can you explain it in more detail?

Students also relied on the chatbot for logistical course information, demonstrating its perceived role beyond academic content delivery. Common questions included:

Which development environment is used at TU Graz for InfoFit?; What exactly is required in this course?; How do I cite correctly?; Can I still pass the course?

It should be noted that only a few examples like these, from our perspective, represent SRL aspects, but are not exactly aligned with Lai’s framework (overall about 5% of the interactions). However, the question arises whether the framework may need to be adjusted here.

4 Discussion

4.1 Key Findings and Interpretation

This study highlights the effectiveness of a retrieval-augmented-generation (RAG) chatbot in supporting self-regulated learning (SRL) within two Austrian university MOOCs. The chatbot was primarily used for factual information retrieval, as evidenced by the high proportion of *seeking - search* (*S.S*, 41%) and *seeking - select* (*S.SL*, 15%) interactions. The chatbot also played a significant role in *engaging - rehearse* (*E.RH*, 17%), with a notable subset of students answering custom multiple-choice questions (120 out of 227 *E.RH* interactions). These findings suggest that students effectively leveraged the chatbot for immediate knowledge acquisition and practice-based reinforcement.

However, engagement with SRL-related activities, such as *goal-setting* (*D.I*, *D.G*, 3% combined) and *self-evaluation* (*R.ES*, 1%), remained low. This aligns with prior research emphasizing that while EdTech can facilitate SRL, students do not automatically adopt SRL strategies [1]. The chatbot's current design primarily focused on delivering accurate responses rather than actively fostering SRL behaviors.

4.2 The Role of AI Chatbots in MOOCs

The chatbot's high adoption rate for factual retrieval demonstrates the strength of RAG-based AI agents in educational settings. Compared to traditional FAQ systems or rule-based chatbots, RAG-enabled responses provided students with accurate and contextually relevant answers, making the chatbot a preferred source of information [3]. However, course-related administrative queries indicate that students also relied on the chatbot for administrative support, such as exam details or citation guidelines. While these queries were handled effectively, embedding such FAQs directly within the course materials could streamline access and ensure consistency.

4.3 The Importance of Quiz-Based Learning in MOOCs

A key takeaway from this study is the importance of quiz-based learning within IBL MOOCs. More than half of the student prompts categorized in rehearsal used the chatbot to answer multiple-choice questions (*120 interactions*). Furthermore, summaries and quiz questions were for the blended learning format, as they reinforced the lecture content and supported knowledge [3]. Prior research on MOOC-based teaching strategies suggests that interactive quizzes are crucial components of effective online learning environments [5].

Given this, an alternative to embedding quizzes within the chatbot itself could be to develop an AI-powered MCQ trainer that dynamically generates questions based on students' prior responses. This would retain the benefits of AI-driven learning while ensuring structured assessment.

4.4 Suggestions for adapting Lai’s framework

About 11% of the chatbot interaction did not fit to Lai’s framework. This is partly, because a significant portion of interactions involves e.g. human like engagements (asking the name of the chatbot) or general knowledge inquiries (how to come from Graz to Vienna). Additionally, we have seen that some interactions might be seen as SRL related interactions, but do not fit into the framework of Lai [10]. While coding the data, we especially had problem to distinguish between interactions fitting into S.SL and E.O as they are very subtle differences.

Building upon this, we would recommend to adapt Lai’s framework concerning we would suggest to adapt "Goal-set" to "Goal Setting and Requirement Clarification (D.G)" and add to the description that this includes attempts to clarify formal requirements.

Then, we suggest to add "Evaluation of Information Quality (S.EQ)" within *seeking* as Action for SRL not mentioned yet in the Lai’s framework [10].

We have as well seen examples, where users not only asked for *re-arranging materials by category* (E.O) but to e.g. translate it or display it as figures. We therefore suggest to add a subcategory called "Reformatting (E.RF)" (or re-working) in *engaging*.

So, our revised framework would look like presented in Table 3:

Table 3. Revision of Process-Action Framework for Chatbot Interactions in SRL (originally by [10]) and example interaction in context of the present study

Process	Action (Code)	Description	Conversation Examples
Defining	Identification (D.I)	Identifying problems or defining an issue to be solved.	I need to understand recursion in Python.
	Goal Setting and Requirement Clarification (D.G)	Setting learning goals or clarifying course requirements.	What do I need to pass this MOOC?
Seeking	Search (S.S)	Retrieving information from the chatbot.	What is a Core Router.
	Select (S.SL)	Extracting key points or requesting summaries.	Summarize the main takeaways from lecture 3.
	Evaluation of Information Quality (S.EQ)	Checking the credibility, reliability, or sources of information.	Where do you get your information from?
Engaging	Review (E.RV)	Revisiting materials or verifying correctness.	Why is this answer correct?
	Organize (E.O)	Structuring content, categorizing information.	List the advantages and disadvantages in order
	Reformatting (Reworking) (E.RF)	Transforming content into a different format (e.g., translation, diagrams, alternative explanations).	Translate this into English. Can you create a flowchart for this?
	Rehearsal (E.RH)	Practicing learned concepts, generating quiz questions.	Give me a quiz about Green IT.
Reflecting	Task Evaluation (R.ET)	Assessing quality of work or readiness to move forward.	Which topic in this lecture has not yet been covered?
	Self-Evaluation (R.ES)	Checking for learning gaps or self-reflection.	What is the best way to study for the InfoFit exam?

4.5 Safeguards Against Prompt Injection and Misuse

A very small number of interaction can be interpreted as attempts of prompt injection techniques, trying to override the chatbot's constraints. However, harmful prompt injection attempts were unsuccessful, as the chatbot consistently maintained its instructional role. For instance, when prompted to behave like a general-purpose chatbot, it responded:

As an educational chatbot for the course "Societal Aspects of Information Technology," I focus on providing information related to the course topics. I cannot assist as a general chatbot, but I am here to help with relevant academic queries.

This resilience was achieved by implementing OpenAI's GPT 4o-mini model with a custom system prompt [6]. However, continuous monitoring and refinement of safeguards remain essential to prevent students from discovering new bypass strategies.

4.6 Future Chatbot Design Considerations

Future chatbots should focus on delivering high-quality responses rather than explicitly enforcing SRL strategies. While SRL competencies are essential for academic success [2], forcing metacognitive questioning may lower student acceptance [3]. A more effective approach is to foster SRL indirectly by integrating goal setting activities, interactive exercises, and AI-generated quizzes, which can naturally encourage self-regulated learning within the learning process.

Additionally, integrating chatbots into course logistics and administrative support could further enhance usability, given the course-related questions. However, care must be taken to ensure that chatbots remain focused on content delivery rather than substituting institutional support systems.

5 Conclusion

This study highlights the strong role of RAG-based AI chatbots in facilitating content retrieval and quiz-based reinforcement in MOOCs. While chatbot interactions primarily revolved around information-seeking and quiz-based learning, the findings suggest that students do not automatically engage in metacognitive learning strategies without explicit support.

Future research should explore how AI-generated quizzes and personalized learning can further enhance learning outcomes. Additionally, refining chatbot safeguards against prompt injection and off-topic interactions remains a key priority. Ultimately, chatbots serve as valuable learning assistants, but their success depends on careful pedagogical design that aligns with student expectations and course goals.

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References

1. Broadbent, J., Poon, W.: Self-regulated learning strategies & academic achievement in online higher education learning environments: A systematic review. *The Internet and Higher Education* **27**, 1–13 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.04.007>
2. Brnner, B., Burgsteiner, H., Schn, S., Ebner, M.: The Synergy of Educational Technologies and Self-Regulated Learning: A Systematic Scoping Literature Review, p. 301–315. Springer Nature Switzerland (2025). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-85649-5_30
3. Brnner, B., Ebner, M.: InfoFit and Beyond: AI Chatbots as EdTech Tools for Self-Regulated Learning in MOOCs. In: Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction. LNCS, Springer, Cham (in press)
4. Ebner, M.: iMooX - a MOOC platform for all (universities). In: 2021 7th International Conference on Electrical, Electronics and Information Engineering (ICEEIE). p. 1–5. IEEE (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/iceeie52663.2021.9616685>
5. Ebner, M., Schns, S.: Inverse Blended Learning, p. 16–26. Routledge (2019). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429398476-2>
6. Etzelstorfer, S.: Comparison of different chatgpt api versions regarding robustness against context breaks using the chatbot in the informatics-fit mooc (2024), unpublished Bachelor's Thesis
7. Gregorac, A., Brnner, B., Ebner, M.: Chatbots in education: A systematic rapid literature review. In: Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference. pp. 652–657. Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE), Orlando, Florida, United States (2025), <https://learntechlib.org/primary/p/225579/>
8. Khalil, H., Ebner, M.: MOOCs Completion Rates and Possible Methods to Improve Retention - A Literature Review. In: Proceedings of World Conference on Educational Multimedia, Hypermedia and Telecommunications 2014. pp. 1236–1244. AACE, Chesapeake, VA (2014)
9. Labadze, L., Grigolia, M., Machaidze, L.: Role of ai chatbots in education: systematic literature review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* **20**(1) (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00426-1>
10. Lai, J.W.: Adapting self-regulated learning in an age of generative artificial intelligence chatbots. *Future Internet* **16**(6), 218 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi16060218>
11. TU Graz Educational Technology, TU Graz Educational Technology: MOOCs & Teaching: Eight Teaching and Learning Scenarios with MOOCs (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3217/TQF22-21458>
12. Zimmerman, B.J.: Investigating self-regulation and motivation: Historical background, methodological developments, and future prospects. *American Educational Research Journal* **45**, 166–183 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831207312909>